

October 28, 2022

To: Professor Helen Whelton. Head of College of Medicine and Health

RE: Expression of interest for Vice Dean of Research and Innovation

Dear Professor Whelton:

Thank you for the opportunity to outline my objectives and qualifications for the role of Vice Dean for Research and Innovation in the College of Medicine and Health, an important and challenging role that I am eager and prepared to take on. For the past seven years, as the Principal Statistician of the Clinical Research Facility at UCC and a Senior Lecturer in Research Methods in the School of Public Health, I have had the unique pleasure of working closely with academics and researchers in each school in the College, as well as the HSE, contributing my methodological expertise to the design and conduct studies, grant applications, research outputs, and ultimately towards improved clinical and public health decision-making. To say I've learned a lot working across so many areas of medicine and health would be an understatement, and I've been fortunate to share many successes with my colleagues. In doing so, I have seen the impressive amount of talent we have in the region, as well as the challenges they face.

The question then is what can I bring to the role of VDRI to help support, develop and multiply that talent, and help ensure we are producing high quality research that benefits patients, public health, and society at large. I have no doubt you will have your choice of many qualified candidates. My particular strengths for this role are evident in a career that is already marked by the support of research excellence in the work of others; a sustained commitment to research integrity and reducing research waste; my expertise in clinical trials; and my fostering of important relationships with colleagues working in our region, as well as those working in important national organizations in the health research landscape, including the HSE, HPSC, DoH, HIQA, CSO, ESRI, HRB, SFI, and other universities.

Developing a culture of grant-seeking

Securing external grant support and funding for our research is critical in the current research environment, and both the CoMH and the university have recently increased investment in grant-seeking. This includes Dr Ashleigh Byrne's important new role in the College; the development of PPI Ignite Cork; the increase in training opportunities organized by the Research Office; and our work in the CRF-UCC, where we have supported dozens of grant applications in the areas of study design, statistics, and research data management. However, grant-seeking among academics in the College is still not the norm, and more work is needed at a cultural level to change that.

As VDRI, I will help lead the development of additional supports, contributing what I've learned while supporting grant applications across the College, and my experience having trained at research intensive institutions in the US where grant-seeking is the norm (Hopkins and UNC). One of the most important things we can do is encourage researchers to develop ideas for grants *before* the call is announced. One of my immediate goals as VDRI will be to work with our schools to identify a cohort of early and mid-career academics each year to participate in a series of in-person workshops on grant development. Topics will include identifying impactful research questions, writing compelling justifications, embedding true PPI, research methods, and data management. I will also recruit more senior academics to share their experiences, and the reviews from their previously funded and unfunded applications. This approach will provide peer support, create connections between researchers across the schools, improve esprit de corps, and increase accountability for grant submission. Similarly, I will organize smaller cohorts of investigators around strategically selected grant calls, and introduce focused support for *unsuccessful* investigators to help them quickly identify new calls to resubmit to, maximizing gains from the considerable work that goes into applying in the first place.

Expanding research data services

Another key to grant success as an organization is to make it easier for investigators to apply while maintaining high standards. One way to do this is to identify widely needed research support services and to provide them at the organizational level, creating economies of scale. We have started down this road with research data management services in the CRF-UCC and as VDRI I would work to expand the CoMH's capacity in this area. Our focus on research data management is driven by a now obvious necessity that we recognized and started to plan for over 5 years ago. High quality research-data management plans are now required by every important research funder, while many funders and publishers require sharable, FAIR research-data outputs when studies are completed and reported. These changes have been driven by both EU and national research policies and are now reflected in the wider UCC research strategy. This has been in direct response to the growing appreciation of the costs of collecting research-data and the need to maximize its value; the importance of data protection and the jeopardy created by data breaches; and wider recognition that poor research-data management can lead to data errors that are then propagated through analyses, results, and interpretations, creating research waste and even harms for patients.

Working with my colleague Dr Brendan Palmer to build a research data management service within the CRC-UCC, we now have considerable expertise and technical skill in this area, allowing my team to efficiently support high quality data management, including development and deployment of electronic data capture platforms, across dozens of studies with a very small staff. This contrasts with each individual study needing to train and then task members of their research team with data management, often very junior members of staff who may not still be involved in the project when it ends. Importantly, we have worked closely with colleagues in the Research Office and the Library to develop and promote this service, and our work was recognized with a *UCC Research Award for Creating a Culture for Responsible Conduct of Research* in 2019. We have also used our position to directly influence the HRB's policies on research data management. As VDRI I will continue to advocate for and develop this pragmatic, strategic approach to supporting data management, and research conduct more broadly.

Supporting Open Research

Given the increasing importance of Open Research in the European research landscape as well as the UCC research strategy, it's vital that the VDRI have a sophisticated understanding of this area, including experience *implementing* open research methods, in order to maximize our research and innovation opportunities. In addition to being a highly visible proponent of Open Research for over a decade, I organized a 3 day workshop on Open Science at UCC in 2018, the first of its kind in Ireland; I worked on the PaPOR trail project, led by Dr Karen Matvienko-Sikar, to develop Open Research training platform for undergraduate students that was recognized with a *UCC Research Award for Open Science* in 2022; and I am partner on two projects recently funded by the National Open Research Forum in their first ever grant call - one of these is led by Dr Aoife Coffee in our library to develop a national network of research data stewards. My commitment to Open Research is also reflected in our work in the CRF-UCC to support FAIR data stewardship and reproducible analysis code, with this later work forming the basis for a postgraduate research skills module.

Enabling investigator-led clinical trials

The HRB and UCC have invested considerably to support the conduct of clinical trials in the region. While this investment has been productive on the whole, there is more work to be done. In particular, the CoMH has not met stated strategic goals for investigator-led regulated clinical trials sponsored by UCC. Despite having all the expertise and capabilities within UCC (Sponsor office, CRF-UCC and OCLA), the University is not currently sponsoring any HPRA regulated clinical trials, while other Universities in Ireland sponsor several (e.g UCD have 5 ongoing regulated CTIMPs). These investigator-led trials are vitally important, as they typically focus on research questions that are highly impactful for patients and the public, but that don't have any obvious commercial value and thus won't find a commercial sponsor or funding. Further, being involved in such research not only improves patient outcomes, but attracts high quality researchers and students to the College.

Thus one of my key motivations to serve as VDRI is to work with university and college leadership and other stakeholders to facilitate such trials, helping to build on the efforts of Professor Joe

Eustace and many others. My experience in this area is considerable. In addition to my work in the CRF-UCC, where I have worked on thirteen academic-led trials including the three largest such trials in Cork, I am a work-package co-lead for developing academic-led trials in the newly funded Cancer Trials Group led by Professor Roisin Connolly. I am also a member of the National Research Ethics Committee for Clinical Trials (A), and have experience working productively with colleagues in the UCC Sponsors Office, as well as those working across our national trials infrastructure, including the other CRFs, the Trials Methodology Research Network, the National Clinical Trials Office, and the HRB funded trials networks.

Connecting UCC and the HSE as research partners

In March of 2021 I was invited to join the Irish Epidemiological Modeling Advisory Group (IEMAG) to NPHET, led by Professor Philip Nolan. My role was to lead the development of a permanent biostatistics and modeling unit within the HSE's Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC). To facilitate this work, I was seconded into the HPSC for 80% FTE in 2021 and 20% FTE in 2022 (which I managed while meeting ongoing responsibilities in the CRF-UCC and the School of Public Health). With the support of the former and current CMOs, and many colleagues in the HPSC and the IEMAG, this effort has been successful, as the budget for the unit was finally approved in August and the head of unit role is now being advertised.

This experience was transformative for me in several ways that will help me as VDRI to work with CoMH leadership to navigate how to best manage the relationship between UCC and the HSE as partners in clinical, health services, and public health research. Having worked in the HSE, I have built up a number of positive, productive relationships within it. I have similarly developed relationships with other IEMAG members, which also includes colleagues from the DoH, CSO, ESRI, HIQA, SFI, every major Irish university, and Insight. Perhaps most importantly, I witnessed firsthand the challenges academic researchers faced in trying to rapidly turn their talent and skills towards the pandemic, when the interface between the HEIs and the HSE was entirely unfit for this purpose, and am supremely motivated to work towards improving it. This will of course have the benefit of creating more research opportunities for the College.

Promoting methodological excellence

In 1994 the British Medical Journal published a short but insightful paper titled *The Scandal of Poor Medical Research* by the late Doug Altman. In that paper, he argued that many peer-reviewed publications in medicine are “misleading because of [their] methodological weaknesses”. Further, he diagnosed the problem as one of misplaced incentives - that the scandal of poor medical research was largely driven by the need for medical researchers to publish for career progression, even when they lack the training and support to conduct high quality research. Altman's seminal paper was before my time, but it was followed 20 years later by a special series in the Lancet that outlined clear evidence that such research waste was still the norm rather than the exception.

Preventable drivers of research waste include poor study designs and improper analyses of research data, factors that I am particularly well suited to address as VDRI, as preventing such

research waste has been my day-to-day focus for most of my career. Put simply, the College does not offer enough methodological support to researchers, certainly not relative to peer organizations, and our methodological training in study design, measurement, biostatistics and health data science are outdated. As a respected epidemiologist and applied statistician, I am well qualified to help the College to remedy these gaps, which will only become more apparent over time. In the near term, I will work with colleagues to develop a new series of postgraduate training modules in experimental design, randomized controlled trials, observational study designs, biostatistics and health data science; and work with the schools to review methodological teaching in the undergraduate curricula. In the longer-term, I would like to work with leadership to eventually establish a centre of excellence in Applied Biostatistics and Health Data Science associated with the College.

Measuring research and innovation

Measuring research and innovation is widely recognized as a difficult challenge, though recent progress at the EU level via COARA, which the HRB are now a signatory to, is encouraging. Importantly, there are considerable risks in getting this wrong, as inappropriate metrics and measurement can create perverse incentives damaging to researchers' careers and research itself, and place hype ahead of real societal impact. As VDRI I would come to this challenge with the advantage of being a methodologist with expertise in measurement and making sense of data without fooling yourself or others. I will also bring my experience in deploying high quality data collection platforms to help ensure that our monitoring efforts are efficient, error-free, and reproducible. I also recognize that assessment of research and innovation is not simply an administrative challenge, but also a scientific one, and will treat it as such. Thus, if given the opportunity, I will immerse myself to better understand research assessment and current efforts to monitor it in Ireland and across the EU; engage the Research Office, the Library and other stakeholders; and spend three years developing a platform for monitoring research and innovation that is the envy of our peers and that will continue to be useful well beyond my tenure as VDRI.

Thank you for your consideration. I look forward to discussing the role with you further.

Sincerely,

Darren L Dahly, PhD
Senior Lecturer, School of Public Health, UCC
Principal Statistician, HRB Clinical Research Facility UCC